

Interpolation Kernel Machines: Reducing Multiclass to Binary

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Abstract. Interpolating classifiers interpolate all the training data and thus have zero training error. Recent research shows their fundamental importance for high-performance ensemble techniques and other advantages. Interpolation kernel machines belong to the class of interpolating classifiers and do generalize well. They have been demonstrated to be a good alternative to support vector machines. In this work we further improve their performance. We propose not to use their inherent multiclass classification capacity, but instead apply them for solving binary classification instances based on a multiclass-to-binary reduction. We experimentally study this ensemble approach in combination with six reducing multiple-to-binary methods. The experimental results show that the one-versus-one scheme consistently demonstrates superior performance.

1 Introduction

Kernel-based methods in machine learning have sound mathematical foundation and provide powerful tools in numerous fields. In addition to classification and regression [12,21], they also have successfully contributed to other tasks such as clustering [25], dimensionality reduction (e.g. PCA [16]), consensus learning [22], computer vision [7], and recently to studying deep neural networks [10].

Interpolation kernel machines [4,15] belong to the class of interpolating classifiers that interpolate all the training data and thus have zero training error [27]. Despite zero training error, they generalize well to unseen test data [4] (a phenomenon also typically observed in over-parametrized deep learning models). Compared to deep neural networks (DNNs), interpolation kernel machines can be interpreted as two-layer neural networks. They turned out to be a good alternative to DNNs, capable of matching and even surpassing their performance while utilizing less computational resources in training [15]. The recent work [29] has shown that interpolation kernel machines are also a good alternative to support vector machines (SVM).

Interpolation kernel machines are capable of handling multiclass classification problems per se. A multiclass classification task, however, can be expected to be

intrinsically more challenging than a binary one in general [20]. This concerns not only the classification but also performance evaluation [1]. We thus propose not to use the inherent multiclass classification capacity of interpolation kernel methods, but instead apply them for solving binary classification instances based on a multiclass-to-binary reduction. We experimentally study an ensemble approach where a multiclass classification problem is reduced to multiple binary ones. Our experimental results demonstrate that the ensemble approach is capable of boosting the performance of interpolation kernel machines.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. We give a brief discussion of interpolating classifiers and introduce interpolation kernel machines in Section 2. We present various reducing multiclass-to-binary methods in Section 3. The experimental results follow in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Interpolation kernel machines

It is commonly believed that perfectly fitting the training data, as in the case of interpolating classifiers, must inevitably lead to overfitting. Recent research, however, reveals good reasons to study such classifiers. For instance, the work [27] provides strong indications that ensemble techniques are particularly successful if they are built on interpolating classifiers. A prominent example is random forest. Recently, Belkin [3] emphasizes the importance of interpolation (and its sibling over-parametrization) to understand the foundations of deep learning.

The so-called kernel machines [4,15] are an instance of interpolating classifiers. Note that this term has been often used to mean variants of SVM (e.g. [13,28]). For the sake of clarity we will use the term ‘‘interpolation kernel machine’’ throughout the paper.

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\} \subset \Omega^n$ be a set of n training samples with their corresponding targets $Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\} \subset \mathcal{T}^n$ in the target space. A function $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$ interpolates this data iff $f(x_i) = y_i, \forall i \in 1, \dots, n$.

Representer Theorem Let $k : \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a positive semidefinite kernel for some domain Ω , X and Y a set of training samples and targets as defined above, and $g : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a strictly monotonically increasing function for regulation. We define E as an error function that calculates the loss L of f on the whole sample set with:

$$E(X, Y) = E((x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n L(f(x_i), y_i) + g(\|f\|) \quad (1)$$

Then, the function $f^* = \operatorname{argmin}_f \{E(X, Y)\}$ that minimizes the error E has the form:

$$f^*(z) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i k(z, x_i) \quad \text{with } \alpha_i \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2)$$

The proof can be found in many textbooks, e.g. [12].

We now can use f^* from Eq. (2) to interpolate our training data. Note that the only learnable parameters are $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$, a real-valued vector with the same length as the number of training samples. Learning α is equivalent to solving the system of linear equations:

$$G(\alpha_1^*, \dots, \alpha_n^*)^T = (y_1, \dots, y_n)^T \quad (3)$$

where $G \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the kernel (Gram) matrix. In case of positive definite kernel k the Gram matrix G is invertible. Therefore, we can find the optimal α^* to construct f^* by:

$$(\alpha_1^*, \dots, \alpha_n^*)^T = G^{-1}(y_1, \dots, y_n)^T \quad (4)$$

After learning, the interpolation kernel machine then uses the interpolating function from Eq. (2) to make prediction for test samples. Note that solving the optimal parameters α^* in (4) in a naive manner requires computation of order $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ and is thus not feasible for large-scale applications. A highly efficient solver EigenPro has been developed [19] to enable significant speedup for training on GPUs. Another recent work [26] applies an explainable AI technique for sample condensation of interpolation kernel machines.

In this work we focus on classification problems. In this case $f(z)$ is encoded as a one-hot vector $f(z) = (f_1(z), \dots, f_c(z))$ with $c \in \mathbb{N}$ being the number of output classes. This requires c times repeating the learning process above, one for each component of the one-hot vector. This computation can be formulated as follows. Let $A_l = (\alpha_{l1}^*, \dots, \alpha_{ln}^*)$ be the parameters to be learned and $Y_l = (y_{l1}, \dots, y_{ln})$ target values for each component $l = 1, \dots, c$. The learning of interpolation kernel machine becomes:

$$G \underbrace{(A_1^T, \dots, A_c^T)}_A = \underbrace{(Y_1^T, \dots, Y_c^T)}_Y \quad (5)$$

with the unique solution:

$$A = G^{-1} \cdot Y \quad (6)$$

which is the extended version of Eq. (4) for c classes and results in zero error on training data. When predicting a test sample z , the output vector $f(z)$ is not a probability vector in general. The class which gets the highest output value is considered as the predicted class. If needed, e.g. for the purpose of classifier combination, the output vector (z) can also be converted into a probability vector by applying the softmax function.

3 Reducing multiple-to-binary methods

Different methods have been reported in the literature to reduce multiclass problems into binary ones [11,18]. Most popular are one-versus-one (OvO), one-versus-all (OvA), and error-correcting output codes [9]. Such methods are mostly

applied to cope with classifiers like logistic regression and SVM that are originally designed for solving binary classification problems only. A few works are concerned with performance comparison of these reduction methods. For instance, comparisons between using OvO and OvA have shown that OvO is better for training SVM [2,14] and several other classifiers [11].

On the other hand, it is not a general practice to apply this reduction-based ensemble approach to classifiers that can handle multiclass classification problems per se. When (deep) neural networks are used for multiclass classification problems, the output layer is typically softmax with one output unit for each class. This is therefore an OvA classification scheme. The work [23] presents an OvO classification method for deep neural networks and demonstrates its superior performance over the OvA scheme in some of the experimental settings. In this work we study the potential of the reduction-based ensemble approach to boost the performance of interpolation kernel machines.

3.1 OvO scheme

Given K classes, $L = K(K - 1)/2$ binary classifiers are generated, each being responsible to differentiate a pair of classes (i, j) , $i \neq j$. Then the output of these base classifiers is combined to predict the final output class. This method, however, has a potential disadvantage in case of many classes. Several strategies have been proposed in [24] to alleviate this drawback of the OvO scheme.

There is a simple trick to avoid training L times, which was also used in [23]. A code matrix M_c of size $K \times L$ is constructed to encode all L pairs of classes, with values 0, -1, or 1. For $K = 4$, for instance, the code matrix is:

$$M_c = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The value 0 means that the output should be indifferent to both classes. Instead of usual practice of using a one-hot target vector y for a neural network, the training is done to achieve yM_c . For example, the trained neural network should ideally output $[0, -1, 0, -1, 0, 1]$ for class 3 with one-hot target vector $y = [0, 0, 1, 0]$. Given an output vector \tilde{y} , the corresponding one-hot target vector is computed by $\tilde{y}M_c^t$.

This nice encoding trick unfortunately does not work for interpolation kernel machines. Without using this trick, the output vector $f(z)$ for some test sample z is given by $f(z) = K_z G^{-1} Y$ according to Eq. (6), where $K_z = (k(z, x_1), \dots, k(z, x_n))$. When we apply the encoding trick above, the interpolation kernel machine intends to achieve $Y M_c$ instead of Y during training. Accordingly, the reconstructed one-hot target vector for test sample z becomes:

$$f_{encoding}(z) = (K_z G^{-1} Y M_c) \cdot M_c^t = K_z G^{-1} Y \cdot (M_c M_c^t)$$

It can be easily shown that matrix $M_c M_c^t$ of size $K \times K$ has $K-1$ on the diagonal and all non-diagonal elements are -1. Thus, $f(z)$ and $f_{encoding}(z)$ are maximal at

the same position. This proves that the encoding trick is not applicable to interpolation kernel machines to achieve cost-effective OvO implementation. Given this fact, we simply use the straightforward pairwise combinations of all classes.

3.2 OvA scheme

Here, K binary classifiers are generated, each being responsible to differentiate one class and the remaining classes. Although the number of base classifiers is considerably reduced, the inherent complexity of each base classifier becomes higher compared to OvO. The deduced binary classification problems may even be not solvable, see [5] for a simple example. Another disadvantage of OvA scheme is the induced imbalance. Even for balanced training data, the ratio of data for one class and the remaining classes is $1 : (K - 1)$. This effect is amplified even more unfavorably for unbalanced training data.

The number of base classifiers can be further reduced from K to one only, which is briefly mentioned in [6]. It is based on transferring the original feature matrix of size $N \times d$ for N training samples of dimension d into another matrix of size $NK \times dK$ that basically encodes all K OvA subtasks. We test this strategy of combining multiple binary subproblems into one, MtO, in our experiments.

3.3 Error-Correcting Output Codes

The error correcting output codes (ECOC) follow the same general idea as in the encoding trick above. The coding matrix M_c of size $K \times L$ has L columns which is a parameter. M_c should be carefully designed. Among others, it was suggested that the class codewords (rows of M_c) must be well separated according to the Hamming distance [9,18]. In this work we use three variants of ECOC:

- Exhaustive code: Following [9] we use an exhaustive code for $K \in [3, 11]$, otherwise a random code is generated.
- Dense code [2]: 10,000 random codes are generated and the code is chosen that has the largest ρ (distance between each pair of rows) and does not have any identical columns.
- Sparse code [2]: The code has $\lceil 15 \log_2(K) \rceil$ columns. Each element has pre-specified probability for all possible values.

4 Experimental results

Experiments were conducted on 14 UCI datasets (see Table 1 for an overview) using the following kernels:

- Addictive χ^2 kernel: $k(x, y) = -\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{(x_i - y_i)^2}{x_i + y_i}$
- χ^2 kernel: $k(x, y) = \exp\left(-\gamma \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{(x_i - y_i)^2}{x_i + y_i}\right)$
- Laplacian kernel: $k(x, y) = \exp(-\gamma \|x - y\|)$

Table 1: Description of UCI datasets

dataset	# instances	# features	# classes
Acoustic	400	50	4
Balance	625	4	3
Car	1728	21	4
Cee	666	49	4
Dermatology	358	34	6
Ecoli	336	7	8
Glass	214	10	6
Hcv	589	13	5
Leaf	340	14	30
New-thyroid	215	5	3
Segmentation	210	19	7
Vehicle	846	18	4
Yeast	1484	8	10
Zoo	101	16	7

Table 2: KM v.s. reducing multiple-to-binary methods (additive χ^2 kernel)

Datasets \ Methods	Methods						
	KM	OvO	OvA	MtO	ECOC exhaustive	ECOC dense	ECOC sparse
Acoustic	44.0	51.9	44.0	45.0	44.0	42.1	43.3
Balance	88.5	86.3	88.5	89.4	88.5	88.5	88.5
Car	77.4	80.9	77.4	77.4	77.4	74.0	74.1
Cee	42.2	43.8	42.2	42.2	42.2	43.1	42.5
Dermatology	97.2	97.8	97.2	96.9	97.2	97.2	97.2
Ecoli	81.1	82.1	81.1	80.5	81.4	79.5	80.7
Glass	86.1	90.0	86.1	85.8	86.1	84.7	76.4
HCV	90.6	92.2	90.6	90.6	90.5	92.5	91.4
Leaf	76.7	88.7	76.7	75.7	69.0	50.3	39.1
New-thyroid	89.8	90.2	89.8	89.3	89.3	89.8	89.8
Segmentation	86.7	79.5	86.7	89.5	86.7	88.1	86.7
Vehicle	75.4	75.9	75.4	75.3	75.4	74.5	74.4
Yeast	57.8	58.6	57.8	57.8	54.5	44.3	53.6
Zoo	97.8	100.0	97.8	96.1	97.8	96.8	92.9
Average	77.9	79.8	77.9	78.0	77.1	74.7	73.6

- RBF kernel: $k(x, y) = \exp(-\gamma\|x - y\|^2)$
- Polynomial kernel: $k(x, y) = (\gamma \langle x, y \rangle + c)^d$
- Sigmoid kernel: $k(x, y) = \tanh(\gamma \langle x, y \rangle + c)$

A grid search was performed to optimize the parameters for each kernel. For each dataset, the optimal values were chosen to achieve the maximal average performance over all seven methods (standard interpolation kernel machine, six reducing multiple-to-binary methods).

The results on the six kernels are shown in Tables 2 to 7. Overall, the OvO scheme turns to be the best-performing variant and shows consistent performance improvement compared to the standard interpolation kernel machine (without reducing multiple-to-binary). On the other hand, all remaining reducing multiple-to-binary methods are not convincing. In particular, the three ECOC variants are rather disappointing. Note that in Table 3 the behavior on dataset Ecoli is somewhat “out of frame”. Except OvO all other variants led to very low accuracy. We also computed the average performance by excluding this dataset

Table 3: KM v.s. reducing multiple-to-binary methods (χ^2 kernel)

Methods Datasets	KM	OvO	OvA	MtO	ECOC exhaustive	ECOC dense	ECOC sparse
Acoustic	80.4	77.4	80.4	76.2	78.9	79.9	77.3
Balance	65.6	71.7	65.6	41.1	68.0	65.6	64.9
Car	83.3	88.6	83.3	78.5	83.5	82.2	82.7
Cee	36.1	35.2	36.1	35.1	31.7	35.9	33.5
Dermatology	97.5	97.5	97.5	96.9	96.9	97.5	96.1
Ecoli	55.6	72.2	55.9	51.7	55.6	59.0	54.9
Glass	90.8	89.4	90.8	85.8	90.4	90.1	90.8
Hcv	96.5	96.0	96.5	95.4	96.5	96.2	96.0
Leaf	87.4	89.1	87.4	86.6	86.8	85.6	86.8
New-thyroid	89.9	90.4	89.9	86.7	90.4	89.9	89.9
Segmentation	85.7	89.0	85.7	85.7	85.7	87.6	87.1
Vehicle	78.4	80.3	78.4	78.4	78.3	75.7	78.9
Yeast	30.2	38.6	30.2	24.3	18.8	17.5	24.3
Zoo	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Average	77.0	79.7	77.0	73.0	75.8	75.9	75.9
Average no Ecoli	78.6	80.2	78.6	74.7	77.4	77.2	77.6

Table 4: KM v.s. reducing multiple-to-binary methods (Laplacian kernel)

Methods Datasets	KM	OvO	OvA	MtO	ECOC exhaustive	ECOC dense	ECOC sparse
Acoustic	78.8	76.8	78.8	73.8	78.8	77.2	77.6
Balance	67.3	67.0	67.3	42.9	72.0	67.3	65.6
Car	83.3	88.6	83.3	32.9	83.5	82.3	82.0
Cee	36.1	35.2	36.1	27.6	31.7	35.8	34.0
Dermatology	97.2	97.2	97.2	95.2	96.4	97.2	96.6
Ecoli	88.7	89.0	88.7	77.3	87.0	87.8	88.2
Glass	97.7	97.0	97.7	96.9	98.0	97.3	96.9
Hcv	95.7	95.7	95.7	93.7	95.7	95.4	95.6
Leaf	88.5	89.0	88.5	82.7	88.2	87.8	86.2
New-thyroid	94.5	94.0	94.5	88.9	93.1	94.5	94.5
Segmentation	91.9	93.3	91.9	91.9	91.9	90.0	90.5
Vehicle	75.5	75.1	75.5	71.4	75.5	75.7	75.6
Yeast	50.7	51.6	50.7	46.8	48.7	47.6	44.6
Zoo	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Average	81.9	82.1	81.9	73.0	81.5	81.1	80.6

to enable an “outlier-free” comparison. Even in this setting OvO behaves favorably. The same can be said to the Polynomial / Sigmoid kernel with “outlier” dataset leaf in Table 6 and 7.

5 Conclusion

Recently, interpolation kernel machines have been demonstrated to have several nice properties. In this work we further improve their classification performance. We proposed not to use their inherent multiclass classification capacity, but instead apply them for solving binary classification instances based on a multiclass-to-binary reduction. We have experimentally studied this easy-to-implement en-

Table 5: KM v.s. reducing multiple-to-binary methods (RBF kernel)

Methods Datasets	KM	OvO	OvA	MtO	ECOC exhaustive	ECOC dense	ECOC sparse
Acoustic	78.3	78.2	78.3	66.1	77.0	77.6	77.1
Balance	58.2	46.8	58.7	42.7	50.3	53.1	52.0
Car	83.3	88.6	83.3	29.3	83.5	84.4	83.9
Cec	36.1	35.2	36.1	27.6	31.7	36.3	35.6
Dermatology	97.5	97.5	97.5	80.8	95.6	97.2	95.0
Ecoli	60.6	71.7	60.6	28.6	60.6	59.7	60.6
Glass	92.9	92.8	92.9	28.0	92.9	91.6	92.2
Hcv	93.9	94.9	93.9	48.0	93.7	93.7	94.0
Leaf	85.0	86.5	85.0	85.0	84.7	83.2	84.9
New-thyroid	81.4	86.1	81.4	56.8	81.4	81.4	80.5
Segmentation	86.2	86.7	86.2	29.0	86.2	85.7	84.3
Vehicle	78.3	79.2	78.3	35.1	77.6	78.4	77.8
Yeast	25.3	37.5	21.5	29.5	23.9	24.4	29.5
Zoo	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Average	75.5	77.3	75.3	49.0	74.2	74.8	74.8

Table 6: KM v.s. reducing multiple-to-binary methods (Polynomial kernel)

Methods Datasets	KM	OvO	OvA	MtO	ECOC exhaustive	ECOC dense	ECOC sparse
Acoustic	72.0	72.9	72.0	65.3	70.9	73.0	68.8
Balance	89.3	89.1	89.3	49.0	89.5	89.3	87.7
Car	70.0	75.1	70.0	70.0	69.6	70.0	71.3
Cec	43.3	44.4	43.3	34.1	42.1	36.8	40.7
Dermatology	86.6	93.5	86.6	86.6	86.6	86.3	89.4
Ecoli	34.3	56.3	34.3	34.3	18.5	34.3	34.3
Glass	62.8	81.8	62.8	62.8	62.8	61.1	64.1
Hcv	91.4	93.1	91.4	73.4	91.4	91.6	91.6
Leaf	18.0	84.1	18.0	14.1	9.5	10.3	11.3
New-thyroid	88.3	89.3	88.3	80.5	87.4	88.3	88.4
Segmentation	76.7	84.8	76.7	64.8	71.0	68.1	67.1
Vehicle	65.7	70.2	65.7	22.6	65.8	64.7	65.6
Yeast	29.2	30.3	29.2	13.3	29.2	16.3	3.7
Zoo	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Average	66.3	76.1	66.3	55.1	63.9	63.6	63.1
Average no leaf	70.0	75.4	70.0	58.2	68.1	67.7	67.1

semble approach in combination with six reducing multiple-to-binary methods. The OvO scheme has consistently demonstrated superior performance.

The general idea of solving binary subtasks (reduction-based ensemble approach) in case of multiclass classifiers is not popular yet. We demonstrated its potential for interpolation kernel machines. The work [23] does the same for deep neural networks. The limitation of this method is the introduced extra overhead, making it less practical for real-time or resource-constrained applications. Fortunately, many real problems do have a small enough number of classes.

The reducing multiple-to-binary methods we studied in this work are rather standard. Recent research has resulted in more sophisticated methods, e.g. [8,17], that have additional potential for the general approach we proposed. In addition, we will also extend the experimental work to other domains like graph data.

Table 7: KM v.s. reducing multiple-to-binary methods (Sigmoid kernel)

Methods Datasets	KM	OvO	OvA	MtO	ECOC exhaustive	ECOC dense	ECOC sparse
Acoustic	69.3	67.5	69.3	64.8	69.3	69.8	69.8
Balance	86.9	86.5	86.9	72.7	86.9	86.9	86.9
Car	74.6	77.1	74.6	21.8	74.6	74.9	69.7
Cec	27.9	32.8	27.9	25.2	28.1	29.1	27.9
Dermatology	90.5	93.0	90.5	69.4	90.5	89.7	91.1
Ecoli	76.3	75.0	76.3	52.3	76.1	73.9	64.7
Glass	72.9	79.1	72.9	49.3	72.9	71.8	70.8
Hcv	82.2	81.3	82.2	80.7	88.3	82.7	81.0
Leaf	33.1	81.6	33.1	35.0	28.9	16.3	17.7
New-thyroid	81.3	81.3	81.3	79.4	80.8	81.3	81.3
Segmentation	48.6	86.2	48.6	64.8	48.6	44.3	47.1
Vehicle	62.6	42.5	62.6	54.3	61.1	62.2	56.1
Yeast	53.0	47.7	53.0	53.0	48.4	46.5	46.5
Zoo	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Average	68.5	73.7	68.5	58.8	68.2	66.4	65.1
Average no leaf	71.2	73.1	71.2	60.6	71.2	70.2	68.7

Acknowledgments

Jiaqi Zhang is supported by the China Scholarship Council (CSC). This research has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778602 Ultracept.

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